

CONDENSATION OF SUCCINIC ANHYDRIDE WITH THE METHYL ETHERS OF DIHYDRIC PHENOLS.

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Succinic anhydride has been condensed with anisole and the methyl ethers of isomeric cresols by Friedel and Crafts' method (Rosenmund and Schapiro, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, 272, 313). Hostmann (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1896, II, 663) obtained a dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid from the condensation of succinic anhydride with resorcinol dimethylether, while Mitter and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 747) obtained β -3:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid by the condensation of succinic anhydride with veratrole. But in both these cases the reaction does not seem to have been studied thoroughly by using different solvents. We have now condensed succinic anhydride with the mono- as well as dimethyl ethers of dihydric phenols by Friedel and Crafts' method using different solvents and the results obtained are given in the following table.

Methyl ether used.	Product obtained.	Yield of the product in different solvents.
Veratrole	β -3 : 4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid	44% in nitrobenzene. 46 in carbon disulphide 64 in acetylene tetrachloride
Guaiacol	Did not condense under any conditions.	
Resorcinol dimethyl ether	β -2 : 4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid	88 in nitrobenzene. 50 in carbon disulphide. 60 in acetylene tetrachloride.
Resorcinol monomethyl ether	β -2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoylpropionic acid	40 in nitrobenzene. 35 in carbon disulphide. 40 in acetylene tetrachloride.
Hydroquinone dimethyl ether	β -2 : 5-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid	70 in nitrobenzene. 40 in carbon disulphide. 45 in acetylene tetrachloride.
Hydroquinone monomethyl ether	Did not condense under any conditions.	

The constitution of the product obtained from veratrole was established by oxidation to veratric acid. The product from resorcinol dimethyl ether could not be oxidised by either alkaline potassium permanganate or sodium hypochlorite to any dimethoxybenzoic acid. Its constitution was, therefore, established by its synthesis by the action of succinic anhydride on the Grignard reagent prepared from 4-iodoresorcinol dimethyl ether. The constitution of the product from resorcinol monomethyl ether follows from the fact that on methylation with dimethyl sulphate and caustic soda it gives a product, identical with the one obtained by the condensation of resorcinol dimethyl ether and succinic anhydride. That the side-chain $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$ is in *ortho*-position to the hydroxyl group is inferred from its colour reactions with ferric chloride in which behaviour it resembles 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid. The constitution of the product from hydroquinone dimethyl ether could not be established by its oxidation to dimethyl gentisic acid. Its constitution was, therefore, established by its synthesis by the action of succinic anhydride on the Grignard reagent prepared from bromohydroquinone dimethyl ether.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Procedure followed for the Condensation of Succinic Anhydride with the Methyl ethers.—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (28 g.) was added in four lots to succinic anhydride (1.2 mol.), the methyl ether (1.2 mol.) and the solvent (100 c.c.) in a round-bottomed flask. Care was taken to see that the temperature did not rise higher than 40°. It was kept at ordinary temperature for 4 hours, decomposed by the addition of ice and hydrochloric acid and distilled with steam to remove the solvent. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered and washed with water. It was then extracted with dilute solution of sodium carbonate, the extract was boiled with the addition of animal charcoal, filtered and acidified. The substance thus obtained was filtered, washed and dried.

β -3:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid, m.p. 162°, is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid; slightly soluble in methyl alcohol and chloroform; insoluble in petrol and benzene. Calcium and barium salts are soluble in water and the silver salt soluble in hot water. (Found: C, 60.35; H, 5.95. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.50; H, 5.88 per cent).

Oxidation of the Above Acid.—To the above acid (1 g.) dissolved in a few c.c. of dilute solution of sodium hydroxide, potassium permanganate

(1.2 g.) in 40 c.c. of water was added. The oxidation was complete in half an hour at ordinary temperature. The precipitated MnO_2 was filtered and the filtrate concentrated and acidified. The substance obtained had m.p. 179° and did not depress the m.p. of an authentic specimen of veratric acid.

The *methyl ester* is soluble in the usual organic solvents and crystallises from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 90° . (Found : C, 61.75 ; H, 6.30. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.90 ; H, 6.34 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 70° . (Found : C, 63.10 ; H, 6.82. $C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 63.16 ; H, 6.77 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was a white granular powder, m.p. 180° , soluble in hot water. (Found : N, 13.94. $C_{13}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 14.24 per cent).

β -2:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid, m.p. 148° , is soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetic acid and hot water. Calcium and barium salts are soluble in water. The silver and lead salts are soluble in hot water. (Found : C, 60.29 ; H, 5.93. Equiv., 236.6. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.50 ; H, 5.88 per cent. Equiv., 238.0).

Synthesis of β -2:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic Acid.—To a boiling suspension of succinic anhydride (5 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.) was added the Grignard reagent, prepared from 4-iodoresorcinol dimethyl ether (11 g.) (Kaufmann and Kieser, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2334), magnesium (1.2 g.) and dry ether (50 c.c.). It was warmed on a water-bath for 15 minutes, decomposed by ice and dilute sulphuric acid. The benzene-ether layer was extracted with dilute solution of sodium carbonate. The sodium carbonate extract on acidification melted at 135° . It has equivalent wt., 237.0 and forms a silver salt soluble in hot water. The mixed m.p. with the product from resorcinol dimethyl ether was 147° . The m.p. of the synthetic product could not be raised by recrystallisation.

The *methyl ester* was a colourless liquid, b.p. $210^\circ/27$ mm. ; $n_D^{20} = 1.54224$. (Found : C, 61.82 ; H, 6.37. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.90 ; H, 6.34 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was a colourless solid, m.p. 70° , soluble in the usual organic solvents but insoluble in petrol. (Found : C, 63.07 ; H, 6.90. $C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 63.16 ; H, 6.77 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* melted at 160° . (Found : N, 14.10. $C_{13}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 14.24 per cent).

β -5-Bromo-2:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid, prepared by brominating the parent acid in aqueous solution, had m.p. 178° . It is soluble in hot ethyl alcohol and acetic acid and insoluble in petrol, benzene and chloroform. (Found : Br, 25.15; Equiv., 321.0. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5Br$ requires Br, 25.13 per cent. Equiv., 317.0).

β -5-Nitro-2:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid, prepared by nitrating the parent acid in glacial acetic acid, had m. p. 173° . It is soluble in hot water, hot methyl and ethyl alcohols and insoluble in chloroform, petrol and benzene. (Found : N, 4.78; Equiv., 281.3. $C_{12}H_{13}O_7N$ requires N, 4.95 per cent. Equiv., 283.0).

β -2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoylpropionic acid, prepared by the condensation of succinic anhydride with resorcinol monomethyl ether, is soluble in hot organic solvents and hot water. It crystallises in fine needles from methyl alcohol, m. p. 156° . Calcium and barium salts are soluble in water and the silver salt insoluble in water. (Found : C, 58.72; H, 5.45. Equiv., 226.0. $C_{11}H_{13}O_5$ requires C, 58.94; H, 5.36 per cent. Equiv., 224.0).

The *methyl ester* is a colourless solid (needles from dilute alcohol), m. p. 85° , soluble in the usual solvents but insoluble in petrol. (Found : C, 60.30; H, 5.80. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.50; H, 5.88 per cent).

The *ethyl ester*, m. p. 68° , has similar solubilities as the methyl ester. (Found : C, 61.78; H, 6.50. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.90; H, 6.35 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* is a white granular powder, m. p. 175° , insoluble in all solvents. (Found : N, 14.73. $C_{12}H_{15}O_5N_3$ requires N, 14.94 per cent).

Methylation of β -2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoylpropionic Acid.—The acid (2 g.), dissolved in 10 c.c. of 10 % solution of sodium hydroxide, was treated with 2 c.c. of dimethyl sulphate and left overnight. It was again treated with the same quantities of dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide and was warmed on a water-bath, cooled and acidified. The substance, m. p. 148° , did not depress the m. p. of *β -2:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid*.

β -2:5-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid, m. p. 107° (prisms from acetic acid) is soluble in hot methyl and ethyl alcohol and hot water, insoluble

in petrol, chloroform and benzene. Calcium and barium salts are soluble in water and the silver salt soluble in hot water. (Found : C, 60.28 ; H, 5.82. Equiv., 240.0. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.50 ; H, 5.88 per cent. Equiv., 238.0).

β -2:5-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid was prepared from bromohydroquinone dimethylether (Noelting and Werner, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3250).

The *methyl ester* crystallised from hot petrol in square plates, m.p. 54°. (Found : C, 61.83 ; H, 6.45. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.90 ; H, 6.34 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 46°. (Found : C, 63.06 ; H, 6.82. $C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 63.16 ; H, 6.77 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methyl alcohol. m.p. 195°. It is insoluble in ethyl acetate, benzene, acetic acid, petrol and chloroform. (Found : N, 13.93. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.24 per cent).

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